

AN IMPROVED PROCEDURE FOR THE PREPARATION OF *sym*-DIARYLTHIO-CARBAMIDES

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A survey of the literature on the preparation of *sym*-diarylthiocarbamides reveals that the most important method required for this purpose involves the use of the interaction of a primary amine with carbon disulphide according to the following equation :

The success of this method depends upon the means employed for effecting the elimination of hydrogen sulphide. The various reagents employed for eliminating hydrogen sulphide are: (a) sulphur (Hugershoff, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2245; (b) potassium or sodium hydroxide (Rathke, *ibid.*, 1873, 5, 799; (c) pyridine (Harry *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 1539) and (d) iodine along with pyridine (Harry *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Of the four methods, (b) and (c) are in general use.

In previous investigations on 3-aryl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones and 3-arylthiazolid-2:4-diones (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 49; 1957, 34, 475; 1958, 35, 576) we had occasion to prepare *sym*-diarylthiocarbamides as starting materials. Studies on the rate of formation of these compounds resulted in a modification of the method (b). This deals with the use of concentrated solutions of potassium carbonate or sodium carbonate in the place of KOH or NaOH solutions. This has been found to furnish better yields than (b) and (c) both. The results of this investigation are briefly discussed here.

Procedure.—The amine (*o*-toluidine, 5 g.), CS₂ (5 c.c.) and ethanol (5 c.c.) were taken in a r.b. flask fitted with a long reflux condenser and the reagent for eliminating H₂S was slowly added. The mixture was heated on a water-bath by varying the time of reflux ranging from 1½ to 3 hours. CS₂ and ethanol were then distilled off and the residue was washed with water and HCl (dil.) to remove *o*-toluidine, if any. The solid was filtered, washed with water and dried. For each time of reflux the corresponding yield was found out. A small portion of the substance in every case was recrystallised from alcohol and its m.p. determined, which was always found to be 161° (lit. m.p. 161°), thus ensuring the purity of the thiourea, thus obtained. It was further confirmed by determining the percentage of sulphur in some cases.

Table I records the variations in yield on using different reagents for eliminating H₂S. Other details were similar as described in the above procedure.

TABLE I

Reagents used.	Yield in terms of time of reflux.			
	1.5 hrs.	2 hrs.	2.5 hrs.	3 hrs.
40% KOH soln. (4 c.c.) ..	3.51 g.	3.88 g.	4.08 g.	4.67 g.
Pyridine (2 g.) ..	..	2.28	2.66	3.02
40% Na ₂ CO ₃ soln. (5 c.c.) ..	4.51	4.54	4.61	4.82
65% K ₂ CO ₃ soln. (5 c.c.) ..	4.60	4.64	4.76	5.17

The success of this modification can be judged by a careful study of the yields of *sym*-di-*o*-tolylthiourea as given above. Extension of this modification to a variety of amines has also been achieved and it has been found that the modification not only affords better yields but also a high degree of purity of the crude product so that recrystallisation has been found to be unnecessary.